

An Ontology-Driven System for Diversity-Aware Human-Robot Interaction Using LLMs

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Abstract—This extended abstract presents a novel system for diversity-aware autonomous conversations using Large Language Models (LLMs). Leveraging a cloud-based architecture and an ontology-driven knowledge base, the system adapts interactions to a wide range of user characteristics. Experiments in both controlled settings and real-world case studies demonstrate the system’s effectiveness in managing complex interactions and sustaining user engagement across various environments.

Index Terms—human-robot interaction, ontology-based dialogue, diversity-aware systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Socially Assistive Robots (SARs) have gained prominence in various fields, including healthcare, education, and domestic assistance. With this growing presence, there is a need for robots to engage in culturally sensitive and diversity-aware interactions. Traditional AI and robotics systems frequently employ stereotype-based approaches that fail to capture individual diversity, including variations in personality, culture, age, gender, and health status [1]. Consequently, these interactions may not align with the user’s unique characteristics, potentially resulting in disengagement or discomfort.

In recent years, the integration of LLMs has shown significant potential for enhancing human-robot interaction [2]. However, effectively utilizing LLMs for real-time, nuanced conversations demands an architecture capable of incorporating diverse, user-specific information. To address this challenge, we propose a cloud-based, ontology-driven dialogue framework that employs LLMs with carefully crafted prompts, enabling contextually tailored interactions.

This work explores the development of a conversational system that adapts interactions based on diversity awareness to enhance user experience. By leveraging an ontology-based structure and advanced prompt engineering, our system provides an autonomous, real-time model for personalized interactions in SARs, addressing the limitations of conventional, context-independent systems.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system builds upon the CAIR (Cloud AI and Robotics) framework [3], incorporating LLMs into its dialogue management service. The architecture, illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of multiple interconnected modules, including the Hub, Dialogue Manager, Plan Manager, and a knowledge base.

Fig. 1. CAIR system architecture integrating LLMs for diversity-aware interactions. Modified or newly added modules are highlighted in blue.

The Dialogue Manager implements addressing policies to effectively regulate the dynamics of multi-party interactions, promoting balanced user participation and reducing the formation of subgroups [4]. Additionally, CAIR integrates functionalities such as speaker registration, speaker recognition, and dense captioning to ground conversations in the visual context when required [5]. The cloud-based architecture further facilitates scalability and adaptability, allowing the system to be deployed across various domains, including healthcare and educational settings.

A. Role of Ontology and Dialogue Nuances

The ontology is fundamental to the system’s diversity-aware capabilities, structuring knowledge to include conversation topics, user preferences, and predefined sentences. Unlike static or stereotype-based models, the system adapts its representation using “dialogue nuances,” which enrich the dialogue state with individualized details and conversational guidelines. Each nuance is encoded as a vector that captures factors such as diversity (e.g., nationality, mental and physical condition), time (e.g., time of day, season, events), place (e.g., environment, city, nation), tone (e.g., humorous, kind, dramatic), and speech act (e.g., assertive, commissive, expressive).

Prompt engineering is essential for incorporating these nuances into the LLM’s sentence generation. Transition matrices guide the prompt design, determining which nuances should be used at each interaction turn. This approach enables the LLM to generate contextually relevant responses that align with the user’s specific characteristics and preferences while maintaining flexibility in conversation.

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Fig. 2. Evolution of the usage of tone nuance values across the first 100 turns using humorous sentences.

B. LLM Integration and Prompt Design

The system employs both GPT-3.5 Turbo and GPT-4o models for specific tasks within the dialogue management process. The interaction with the LLMs is structured around four types of requests: (1) the Topic Request identifies the most suitable conversation topic from a predefined list in the ontology, facilitating contextually relevant dialogue; (2) the Sentiment Request evaluates the user’s input to detect preferences or aversions, allowing the system to adapt its responses accordingly; (3) the Reply Request generates a response that directly addresses the user’s input by incorporating dialogue nuances for contextual relevance; and (4) the Continuation Request advances the conversation by selecting relevant follow-up topics from the ontology and generating contextually appropriate sentences using dialogue nuances. This methodology enables the system to maintain a balance between diversity awareness and effective control over the conversation flow.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Diversity-Aware Robotics: Performance Tests

Controlled experiments, using 300 pre-scripted sentences generated by ChatGPT (GPT-3.5), were conducted to evaluate the system’s performance in topic recognition, sentiment analysis, dialogue nuance adaptation, and the “diversity cost” in terms of tokens (units of text used by OpenAI’s models to process requests). These sentences were generated in three different tones – humorous, aggressive, and neutral – to simulate diverse conversational contexts.

The system recognized conversation topics in 87.33% of cases, covering 48 different ontology topics. This high recognition rate underscores the effectiveness of the ontology-guided prompt design and the LLM’s capability to handle diverse conversational content. On average, the “diversity cost” was 329 tokens per interaction turn, reflecting the computational effort required to incorporate nuanced information.

Figure 2, depicts how the tone recognized in the first 100 humorous sentences correlates with an increase in the usage of the humorous tone nuance. Eventually, the overall usage of the dialogue nuances aligns with the expected one from the

steady-state distribution computed starting from the transition matrices. This result validates the system’s real-time capability of managing diversity-aware conversations.

B. Real-World Case Studies

Two real-world case studies further evaluated the system’s adaptability. In the first, the system was deployed at public exhibitions, including the “Maker Faire” in Rome and the “Festival della Scienza” in Genoa. Over seven days, it interacted with hundreds of visitors, resulting in 1,800 conversation turns across 244 topics, demonstrating its robustness in noisy, crowded environments and its potential for public-facing applications. The second case study involved the NAO robot in the home of a paraplegic woman. Over six days, the robot completed 1,003 dialogue turns, exploring 166 topics. The participant expressed a sense of companionship and empathy, highlighting the system’s potential to provide social support for vulnerable individuals.

A video demonstrating diversity-aware interactions with various robots connected to the CAIR cloud in different environments and languages is available on YouTube¹.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces a diversity-aware conversational system that integrates LLMs into an ontology-driven dialogue framework. Using prompt engineering and nuanced dialogue management, the system adapts to individual characteristics, enhancing user interaction and engagement. Controlled experiments and real-world case studies confirm its effectiveness in managing diverse conversational contexts, with potential applications in healthcare, education, and home environments. Future research will focus on refining the prompt design and expanding dialogue nuances to further enhance the system’s adaptability in complex scenarios.

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¹<https://youtu.be/hfEkNEt0GXc>